

**Generosity and support fund
Qodirova Mamlakat Mominovna**

**Karshi State University, Department of History of Uzbekistan, Candidate of
History, Associate Professor**

Key words: generosity, kindness, national traditions, charity, savings, pandemic, humanity.

Annotation: This article explains that generosity, kindness, helping each other is an ancient value for the Uzbek people, and therefore the Foundation "Generosity and Help" was established. Explanations about the purpose of this fund, its tasks, and the public fund are given.

The Uzbek people are a people whose values have been glorified, and the human factor is at the top of the list[1]. National values and nationalism are still alive, no matter how many times and eras have passed. In the traditional Uzbek values, kindness, honesty, Human virtues[2:1492-1495] such as purity, justice, honesty, love of the country, respect for the country, hard work, patience, humility, courage, generosity, patience, hospitality, charity are glorified. It is a priceless wealth created in the process of development and passed down to generations as a sacred heritage. It is the human duty of every Uzbek citizen to preserve spiritual wealth, pass it on to the younger generation, and further refine it. The traditions[3:135-138] that we have been living in our consciousness: greeting, keeping a family, respecting parents, maintaining health, learning, wearing clothes, honoring bread, and doing good to people, each of them is a great school. A person should always do good, help those around him, lighten their burdens, and live by wanting[4:1-6] goodness for himself and others. Many great national traditions of the Uzbek people, including being kind to each other, showing generosity, patting the heads of needy people in difficult and trying days, are ingrained in our blood, and our traditions have passed through the ages. is undergoing tests. Especially, this situation[5:96-100] showed its reality during the pandemic. In this difficult and trying situation, our whole society worked hand in hand and arrived safely[6:121-123] to these bright days. They set an example and became a strong source of confidence and encouragement for our people.

As a proof of this, based on the order[7:128-131] of the head of our state No. 213 dated April 22, 2020, the Foundation "Generosity and Support" and its divisions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, provinces, Tashkent city and district were established[8:128-132]. On April 20, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev put forward a proposal to start a movement called "Everybody should do meritorious work every

day". The fund and its divisions are opened under the "Mahalla" charitable public fund and its territorial divisions, they are not considered legal entities. Funds can be transferred to the fund in both national and foreign currency. For this purpose, separate sum and currency accounts of the fund are opened in commercial banks.

Therefore, any legal and natural[9:73-76] persons who are residents of Uzbekistan or foreign countries, including entrepreneurs, who wish to sponsor and donate, can direct funds to this fund in national and foreign currency. Helping people's families with love and respect is an example of merit and patriotism for entrepreneurs and farmers, representatives of economic associations, employees of ministries, offices and organizations[10], and in general for any person. The funds received into the "aid" fund are intended to help families with many children, people with disabilities, single elderly people, and individuals who are temporarily unemployed in need of social protection during the coronavirus pandemic and quarantine. The funds of the fund are formed[11:59-63] at the expense of sponsorship and charity funds, other sources not prohibited by law. In addition, Decree No. 346 of July 29, 2020 financial aid was distributed to families in need of social protection[12:73-76] through the "Generosity and Support" fund. State and public control over the use of funds to the "Generosity and Support" fund is established. it was determined that the information about their receipt and use would be announced in the mass media. Such transparency served[13:86-90] to ensure public control. The State Financial Control Offices of the Ministry of Finance constantly monitor the purposeful use of funds. In addition, there is no doubt that law enforcement agencies will ensure control within the scope of their authority. We are sure that "Generosity and help" the activity[14:386-391] of the foundation has remained in history as another example of humanitarianism and generosity of our people. During the Second World War, more than 1 million people of different languages and religions The nation that sheltered many refugees, took most of the 200,000 orphans into their families and brought them up as their own children, today managed to get their compatriots who[15:292-296] need help out of a difficult situation. In total, more than 194 billion 625 million soums of donations have been received. Alisher Usmanov donated 5 million US dollars to the national movement "Generosity and Help" at the briefing held at AOKA. Information was given about ``I. It is noted that these donations will go to 19,009 people in need of social protection, those with many children, the disabled, single elderly people, whose list was submitted by Andijan, Namangan, Tashkent regions[16:26-28] and Tashkent city hokimities. 2.5

million soums - a total of 47,522,500 soums - were distributed to unemployed citizens who temporarily lost their income by transferring them to plastic cards.

393 million 857 thousand soums of various forms of assistance were provided to 824 citizens in need of social protection and difficult family conditions from the funds of the "Generosity and Compassion" fund. In particular, 822 low-income, orphaned, single citizens living in the region were provided with flour products worth 376 million 530 thousand soums and medicines to restore their health. In addition, 17 million 327 thousand soums of material aid was provided for the treatment of 2 citizens living in "Temir Daftar" with health problems.

In particular, in the city of Chirchik, Tashkent region, activities to support the population in need of social protection through the "Generosity and Support"[17] fund are ongoing. More than 1 billion 252 million soums were attracted for social support of the families whose list was formed by Chirchik city division of "Mahalla" charitable public fund. According to the relevant decision of the Chirchik City Council of People's Deputies, up to now 4 thousand Food products were distributed to 188 families. Such charity work was organized by the "Generosity and Support" foundation.

In addition, on April 9, 2022, a meeting on improving the conditions in social institutions was held at the 102nd boarding school for hearing-impaired children in Tashkent. At the beginning of his speech, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev remembered the verse "The reward of goodness is only goodness". Exalting human dignity, supporting people in need of love and help is an important direction of the social policy of our country. Because generosity is the highest example of humanity.

List of used literature

1. A.Madaminov "Saxovat va ko`mak" jamg`armasi haqida. 2020.
2. Hasanov, A. (2020). Kesh-Shakhrisabz oasis in the middle ages. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 29(5), 1492-1495.
3. Khudaykulovich, E. A. (2022). Guzar'sethymology in Historical Sources. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 2(3), 135-138.
4. Muminovich, H. A. (2022). TERRITORIAL AND GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF THE CITIES OF THE TERMIZ OASIS IN THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 6, 1-6.
5. Khasanov, A. M. (2021). Historical and Geographical Regions of Chaghaniyan. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 1(4), 96-100
6. Karimov, B. (2021). Historical Geography of Yakkabog District. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 1(4), 121-123.

7. Xudaykulovich, E. A. (2022). Handicraft and Trade in Guzar District. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 1(8), 128-131.
8. Eshov, B. J., & Hasanov, A. M. (2016). CERTAIN REASONINGS ABOUT ANCIENT LOCAL POPULATION AND THE NOMADIC OF CENTRAL ASIA. Education Transformation Issues, (1), 128-132.
9. Muminov, U. (2021). Historical Gates of Karshi. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 1(6), 73-76.
10. Xudoyqulovich, B. K. D. E. A. (2021). HISTORICAL GEOGRAPHICAL CLASSIFICATION AND ECONOMIC, SOCIO-POLITICAL CLASSIFICATION OF THE GUZAR DEPARTMENT IN THE SECOND HALF OF THE XIX CENTURY CONDITION. Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol, 27(5).
11. Bahrom, K. (2022). SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE AND ADMINISTRATIVE TERRITORY OF SHAKHRISABZ PRINCIPALITY IN THE 19TH CENTURY. Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research, 3(09), 59-63.
12. Muminov, U. (2021). Historical Gates of Karshi. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 1(6), 73-76.
13. Bahrom, K. (2022). Political-Administrative Territory of The City of Karshi in The Second Half of The 19th Century-The Beginning of The 20th Century. International Journal of Scientific Trends, 1(2), 86-90.
14. Мўминов, У. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE CITY OF KARSHI IN FOREIGN TRADE. JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH, 2(14), 386-391.
15. Khudoykulovich, E. A. (2023). ISSUES OF THE HISTORICAL-GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF GUZAR DISTRICT. JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH, 2(14), 292-296.
16. Matluba, R. (2022). THE ROLE OF THE HISTORICAL MONUMENTS OF THE KASHKADARYA OASIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 6, 26-28.
17. "Saxovat va ko`mak" jamg`armasini tashkil etish to`g`risida farmoyish: T.-2020.

